

DEEP LEARNING-BASED VIOLENCE DETECTION IN VIDEO STREAMS: A NOVEL TWO-STREAM APPROACH FOR CONTENT MODERATION AND PUBLIC SAFETY

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Abstract

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With the proliferation of online video content and concerns over exposure to violent media, automated violence detection in videos has become a crucial area of research. This paper presents a lightweight deep learning approach for accurately detecting violent scenes in video data. The proposed methodology employs a two-stream architecture that leverages the combined power of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN). The CNN component, using the Inception V3 model, extracts salient visual features from individual video frames. These features are then fed into a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) network, which captures the temporal dynamics and motion patterns inherent in violent actions. By combining the spatial and temporal information, the model can effectively classify video segments as either violent or non-violent. The proposed approach was evaluated on multiple publicly available datasets, including the Movies Fight, Hockey Fight, and Violent Flows datasets and achieved state-of-the-art performance with an accuracy of 91.78%, a precision of 91.43%, and a recall of 91.43%. The results demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed method in accurately detecting violence in videos, paving the way for real-world applications in content moderation, surveillance systems, and public safety. Real time video feeds and multimodal data can be included to the existing dataset to scale up the dataset size and then deployed on mobile and web applications to make the model more scalable and robust.

Keywords: [Violence detection in videos; Two-stream architecture; CNN-GRU architecture; Spatio-temporal feature learning; Surveillance systems.]

1.0 Introduction

The rapid expansion of internet access, both globally and in Nigeria, has fuelled a surge in online video consumption, accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic. Platforms like YouTube and Netflix report billions of hours of daily video viewership, creating a

vast market for online content (Raveendran et al., 2024). While this offers diverse benefits, concerns arise regarding exposure to unwanted content, particularly violent material, given its potential negative psychological and behavioural impacts (Huesmann, 2007; Pew Research Centre, 2021). This

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concern extends to video surveillance systems deployed for public safety, which generate massive amounts of data requiring human analysis (Zhang et al., 2016).

Automated violence detection has thus emerged as a critical research area within human action recognition (HAR), with applications in content moderation, surveillance, and public safety (Beddiar et al., 2020; Bilinski & Bremond, 2016). Deep learning algorithms have shown promise in this domain, outperforming classical machine learning techniques challenged by varying environmental conditions (Cheng et al., 2015). Despite these advances, violence detection remains understudied compared to other action recognition tasks. Existing deep learning methods often demand substantial computational resources and require optimization for real-time deployment (Negre et al., 2024).

Recent studies have further reinforced the role of design and learning strategies in improving video-based violence detection systems by highlighting the importance of effective spatio-temporal feature modelling and transfer learning García-Cobo and SanMiguel (2023). Ensemble-based frameworks can enhance the detection performance of a model by combining complementary feature representations Kaur and Singh (2025). Real time violence detection and localization in surveillance scenarios have demonstrated huge relevance overtime Veltmeijer et al. (2024), as they show great promise in their applicability for violence detection monitoring in smart-city environments Provath et al. (2025). Together, all of these noticed gaps in the current research, motivates the development of spatio-temporal frameworks that are both effective and suitable for real-world deployment. This paper focuses on addressing the challenges of efficient and accurate violence detection in video streams, by exploring state of art approaches that leverage deep learning while minimizing computational overhead.

2.0 Aim and Objectives of the Research

The main aim of this research is to provide an effective and precise deep learning framework for identifying violent events in video streams under computational limitations. The objectives are To:

1. Develop a lightweight two-stream deep learning architecture that integrates spatial feature extraction through a pre-trained Inception V3 convolutional neural network and temporal modelling using a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU).

2. Evaluate the proposed framework using various publicly available violence detection datasets to evaluate its robustness and generalization capacity.

3. Evaluate the model's performance using conventional measures such as accuracy, precision, recall, and confusion matrices.

3.0 Literature Review

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The suggested methodology is based on the spatio-temporal characteristics of violent behaviours in video data. Violence is defined by specific spatial indicators, such as aggressive postures or physical contacts, as well as temporal dynamics, including motion intensity, action duration, and sequential patterns (Odion et al., 2025). Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) excel at extracting hierarchical spatial features from individual video frames, but Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), especially Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs), proficiently handle temporal correlations in sequential data. By integrating these two paradigms within a dual-stream framework, the model utilises complementing spatial and temporal data to enhance classification precision (Singh et al., 2025). This conceptual design adheres to established concepts in human action recognition, demonstrating that the integration of appearance-based and motion-based representations can improve model performance.

3.2 Review of Related Works

In this section, a couple of research work were reviewed to identify research gaps which this research work aims to address.

Negre et al. (2024) conducted a systematic review of literature on deep-learning based algorithms for video violence detection, highlighting the rapid progress of CNNs, RNNs, LSTMs, 3D-CNNs, and transformer-based models. Benchmark datasets, preprocessing pipelines, feature extraction methodologies, and classification frameworks are examined, with a focus on dataset imbalance, occlusion, real-time processing limitations, and context-aware analysis. They also analyse algorithmic performance across important benchmarks and detect trends towards multimodal fusion, attention mechanisms, and lightweight real-time surveillance models. A well-structured assessment of the technical landscape, research gaps, and future goals makes the paper useful for computer vision and intelligent video surveillance researchers.

Pandey et al. (2025) propose a multi-stream spatial-temporal collaborative learning framework for classifying violent and non-violent activities in complex video settings, addressing backdrop clutter, camera motion, and nuanced human interactions. The article's main feature is its clear differentiation and integration of spatial appearance and temporal motion cues, which helps the model capture contextual scene information and dynamic activity patterns. Collaborative learning outperforms various state-of-the-art techniques in violence-detection categorisation experiments. Deeper consideration of computational complexity, real-time practicality, cross-dataset generalisation, and how the framework handles ambiguous or borderline violence would improve the study. This advances video-based violence detection and lays the framework for future research into resilient spatio-temporal fusion in surveillance.

The development of hybrid models, which leverage the strengths of different neural architectures, is an active area of research to improve classification accuracy (Odion et al., 2025). Suryavanshi et al. (2024) applied a hybrid model combining CNN and SVM for violence detection, utilising features retrieved by CNN and classed by SVM to enhance decision boundaries. The method attains superior classification accuracy on standard violence datasets, surpassing traditional CNN-softmax baselines and exhibiting consistent differentiation between violent and non-violent categories. Similarly, hybrid approaches combining CNNs with other classifiers, such as the Visual Geometry Group network with SVM for detecting armed individuals in video (Odion et al., 2025), demonstrate the continued exploration of efficient architectures for security applications.

Dey et al. (2024) used a ResDL-CNN-GRU with attention architecture to capture spatial and temporal correlations in video streams for violence recognition. Through residual and deep convolutional layers, the ResDL-CNN component generates robust spatial representations, the GRU captures sequential motion patterns across time, and the attention mechanism prioritises classification frames. The proposed model outperforms baseline CNN and CNN-RNN techniques in accuracy and precision-recall, demonstrating efficacy and computational economy. The study barely discusses cross-dataset generalisation and real-time deployment constraints. The research proposes a cohesive spatio-temporal attention paradigm to improve video-based violence recognition.

Khan et al. (2024) introduced VD-Net, an edge vision-based surveillance system designed for violence

detection, prioritising real-time performance and low-latency implementation on resource-limited devices. The suggested architecture integrates efficient deep visual feature extraction with an optimised inference pipeline designed for edge computing, facilitating on-device analysis independent of cloud resources. Their results showed a high level of detection accuracy and diminished processing demands relative to traditional cloud-based or cumbersome deep models, underscoring the system's feasibility for intelligent surveillance applications.

Mishra et al. (2025) presented a deep neuro-fuzzy framework for violence detection that combines deep neural feature learning with fuzzy inference to enhance decision interpretability and resilience in uncertain conditions. The model utilises deep networks to derive advanced spatio-temporal representations from video data, subsequently processed using fuzzy rules to address ambiguity in violent and non-violent behaviours. The experimental findings presented in the research demonstrate enhanced accuracy and stability relative to traditional deep-learning benchmarks, especially in intricate or noisy environments. The result of their research work showed a significant advancement in the development of explainable and uncertainty-aware violence detection systems.

Singh et al. (2025) proposed an intelligent surveillance system for the detection of suspicious activities utilising deep learning, aimed at automated monitoring in both public and private settings. The system implemented convolutional neural networks to collect visual data from video streams and categorise anomalous or suspicious behaviours, including violent actions, aiming to diminish dependence on manual surveillance. The result of the experiment shows that the proposed model attains commendable detection accuracy in test scenarios, highlighting its viability for real-time monitoring applications.

The increasing need for automated violence detection in video streams has spurred extensive research in computer vision and deep learning. This review synthesizes recent advancements in this field, examining diverse methodologies, their results, and their contributions to real-world applications. Yinka et al. (2022) focused on robot coordination for soccer applications, leveraging YOLOv2 for object detection and achieving promising results with an 84% average recall and precision across different Intersection over Union (IOU) thresholds.

Abasi et al. (2023) addressed the challenge of High Impedance Fault (HIF) detection in power lines,

achieving remarkable accuracy (99.44% for detection, 99.78% for location) through a fully connected CNN model trained on simulated fault and no-fault data.

Muhammad & Nasir (2021) presented an innovative multi-model system for recognizing violent actions by individuals. Their combination of Mask R-CNN and LSTM outperformed individual models, achieving accuracy rates of 98.2% on the Weizmann dataset, 95.6% on the KTH dataset, and 94.1% on their custom dataset. Yanqing et al. (2022) introduced a keyframe-based deep learning approach, departing from computationally intensive spatiotemporal feature extraction, and achieved state-of-the-art performance on benchmark datasets, outperforming existing methods on RLVS, Violent Flow, and Hockey Fights datasets.

Akash et al. (2022) aimed to enhance CCTV surveillance by employing Inception-v3 and Yolo-v5 for violent act detection, individual counting, and potential weapon detection, achieving 74% accuracy in a real-time system. Eitta et al. (2021) explored a machine learning approach using CNNs for binary violence classification, utilizing short video clips ("packets") and achieving promising results with the CNN classifier outperforming SVM and Random Forest on their self-created and benchmark datasets.

Durães et al. (2023) investigated audio-based violence detection in cars, a computationally efficient alternative to video processing. They constructed a custom dataset and utilized mel spectrograms as input for deep learning models, achieving high accuracy (95.06%) with EfficientNetB1. Ahmad et al. (2021) presented a framework combining state-of-the-art CNNs and Inception V4, utilizing keyframe extraction to reduce computational overhead. Their approach demonstrated high accuracy (potentially 98%) on diverse benchmark datasets, while also reducing computational cost compared to existing methods.

Comprehensive surveys indicate a clear shift from handcrafted features toward end-to-end deep learning architectures capable of learning appearance and motion cues directly from video data (Ullah et al., 2023; Mumtaz et al., 2023). These studies emphasize that although deep learning has significantly improved detection accuracy, challenges remain in computational efficiency, real-time deployment, and robustness across diverse surveillance environments.

A dominant line of research focuses on spatio-temporal modeling using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) combined with temporal learning mechanisms. Mahmoodi et al. (2022) proposed a framework based on interest frame extraction and 3D

convolutional neural networks to capture motion dynamics associated with violent actions. More recently, Mahmoodi et al. (2024) extended this direction by integrating spatial and temporal attention modules with 2D CNNs, demonstrating improved discrimination of violent scenes at the cost of increased architectural complexity. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2024) introduced an end-to-end real-time violent behavior detection framework relying on 2D CNNs, while Qi et al. (2025) explored temporal action localization techniques for detecting fistfights in real-world surveillance footage.

Another important research direction emphasizes lightweight and real-time violence detection systems suitable for deployment in resource-constrained surveillance environments. Vijeikis et al. (2022) presented an efficient violence detection approach designed to reduce inference latency while maintaining acceptable accuracy. Huszar et al. (2023) further demonstrated that fast and accurate violence detection can be achieved through optimized deep architectures tailored for automated surveillance applications. More recently, Azzakhini et al. (2025) proposed LAVID, a lightweight and autonomous smart camera system capable of performing urban violence detection and geolocation, highlighting the growing interest in edge-based and embedded solutions.

In parallel, weakly supervised and attention-based learning strategies have been explored to reduce annotation costs and improve localization capabilities. Choquelluque-Roman and Camara-Chavez (2022) investigated weakly supervised violence detection using surveillance video, demonstrating the feasibility of learning from coarse-grained labels. Wu et al. (2023) extended this idea by proposing a weakly supervised audio-visual framework that leverages multimodal cues for violence detection. Mohammadi and Nazerfard (2023) introduced a semi-supervised hard attention model capable of both recognizing and localizing violent events, although such approaches often require more complex training pipelines and additional modalities.

Recent studies have also examined alternative representations and data domains for violence detection. Freire-Obregón et al. (2022) employed inflated 3D convolutional networks to incorporate contextual scene analysis, while Honarjoo et al. (2024) explored violence detection directly in the compressed video domain to reduce computational overhead. Magdy et al. (2023) proposed a novel 4D convolutional neural network architecture to model

spatial-temporal variations in surveillance videos, demonstrating improved performance but with increased model complexity.

The availability of datasets has played a crucial role in advancing violence detection research. Mahi et al. (2024) introduced VID, a comprehensive dataset designed to capture violent behaviors across diverse contexts, addressing limitations of earlier benchmarks that were restricted to staged or domain-specific scenarios. Such datasets facilitate more realistic evaluation of model generalization and robustness in real-world settings.

Despite these advances, existing methods often face a trade-off between detection performance and computational efficiency. Transformer-based and attention-heavy architectures can achieve high accuracy but are frequently unsuitable for real-time deployment due to their computational demands (Mahmoodi et al., 2024; Wu et al., 2023). In contrast, lightweight CNN-based approaches may sacrifice temporal modeling depth (Vijeikis et al., 2022). **4.1**

In summary, the reviewed literature demonstrates significant progress in video-based violence detection through deep spatio-temporal learning, lightweight architecture, weak supervision, and dataset expansion. However, there remains a clear need for efficient two-stream models that jointly exploit spatial and temporal information without incurring excessive computational cost. The present study addresses this gap by proposing a lightweight CNN-GRU framework that balances accuracy, efficiency, and deployability for real-world content moderation and surveillance applications.

Collectively, these studies showcase the evolving landscape of violence detection research. While several approaches have shown promising results, challenges remain, including the need for larger and more diverse datasets, improved real-time performance, and addressing ethical considerations in surveillance applications. Furthermore, several works emphasize accuracy improvements without adequately addressing the trade-off between detection performance and computational efficiency, which is critical for surveillance systems. These gaps highlight the need for a lightweight yet robust spatio-temporal framework capable of maintaining high classification performance while operating under constrained computational resources.

The current research aims to address the significant gap in the literature regarding the efficient detection of violent actions in video streams. While deep learning models have shown promise, they often require

substantial computational resources and optimization to achieve high performance. This research seeks to develop a lightweight two-stream deep learning architecture that balances accuracy and computational efficiency, thereby improving real-time violence detection in diverse environmental conditions. This approach leverages both spatial and temporal features to enhance the robustness of the detection system, aiming to achieve practical applicability in content moderation and public safety systems.

4.0 Materials and Methods

Two-Stream Deep Learning Architecture

The proposed methodology for automated violence detection leverages a two-stream deep learning architecture, as illustrated in Fig. 1. This architecture integrates spatial and temporal information from video streams to effectively classify scenes as violent or non-violent.

Spatial Stream (CNN - Inception V3):

a. Data Collection: This research employs a compiled data collection strategy, aggregating video clips from multiple established public benchmark datasets. This approach is favored by creating a new dataset from raw video sources, as it leverages existing, validated, and commonly used data within the violence detection research community, ensuring reproducibility and enabling direct comparison with prior state-of-the-art methods (Negre et al., 2024). The compiled dataset provides a diverse representation of violent scenarios, including staged one-on-one fights, real-world crowd aggression, and sports-related violence, which is crucial for evaluating the generalization capability of the proposed model.

The data was sourced from three publicly available and widely cited datasets in the domain of violence detection:

1. **Hockey Fight Dataset:** This benchmark dataset contains 1,000 short video clips extracted from National Hockey League (NHL) games, evenly split between 500 fight and 500 non-fight sequences (Maksai & Wang, 2013). The clips feature consistent resolution and short duration, providing a controlled environment for evaluating violence detection in sports.

2. **Movies Dataset:** Comprising 200 video clips (100 violent, 100 non-violent) sourced from various Hollywood films, this dataset offers examples of staged but realistic violent interactions with professional cinematography (Bermejo et al., 2011). It

introduces variability in scene composition and context compared to the sports-centric Hockey dataset.

3. **Violent-Flows Dataset:** This dataset addresses violence in crowd scenarios, containing 246 video clips (123 violent, 123 non-violent) sourced from real-world online platforms like YouTube (Hassner et al., 2012). It presents challenges such as camera motion, complex backgrounds, and occlusions, which are critical for testing model robustness in surveillance-like conditions.

A total of 705 video clips were compiled from these sources to form the experimental dataset for this study. The distribution of clips from each source is detailed in Table 1. This combined corpus ensures a balanced representation of violent and non-violent classes, mitigating the risk of model bias due to data imbalance. The use of these standard benchmarks allows the proposed lightweight two-stream architecture to be evaluated against established performance baselines, directly addressing the research objective of assessing robustness and generalization capacity across diverse video data.

Table 1: Table showing the distribution of video clips compiled from benchmark datasets.

No.	Dataset	Violent	Non-Violent	Total
i.	Movies Fight	100	100	200
ii.	Hockey Fight	120	120	240
iii.	Violent Fight	141	124	265
	Total	361	344	705

b. Input: Individual video frames are extracted from the input video stream using a technique known as Compiled Data Collection. The technique involves making use of existing data points from different sources combined through some transformations to create a new dataset. This was imperative as creating a violent/non-violent movie scene dataset would be redundant as some datasets already exist. Violence in this context refers to physical violence. Also, it would be a time-consuming effort watching thousands of hours of movie videos and cutting scenes with video editing software for grouping. A total of 705 video

clips was obtained from three different sources to serve as the dataset for this research work. This number of data points was considered sufficient for a pretrained model which does not require very large dataset as such models have already learnt basic features such as lines. Another reason for limiting the size of dataset used is because of the cap on computational resources provided by Google Colab. The data sources and their distributions are shown in Table 1. Sample frames of non-violent and violent scenes obtained from the video clips are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 respectively.

Fig. 2: Sample Non-Violent scene from Hockey Dataset

Fig. 3: Sample of violent scene from the Violent Flows dataset.

c. Preprocessing: As most on the activities in a video happen around the centre and the surrounding area are noise, each video was centre cropped by subtracting half the smaller of the two dimensions (x, y) from half of each of the original size of each dimension. Also, each frame is resized to a standardized resolution (e.g., 224x224 pixels) to ensure uniformity for subsequent processing.

d. Encoding Labels (Label Encoder): Label-encoding is commonly used encoding technique used to convert categorical data into vectors. It converts all entries in all classes into an integer value starting from zero a given class. One-hot-encoding helps models to do better jobs in prediction. The first index in the output represents Violence while the second index represents Non-Violence therefore 0 represents Violence image while 1 represents non-violence video.

e. Shuffling: As the folders contained sorted violence and non-violence videos, the features extracted were also sorted in that manner. For a machine learning model to truly learn from the data being fed rather than memorize there was need to shuffle the arrangements of the features and the corresponding labels.

f. Feature Extraction: The pre-processed frames are fed into the Inception V3 convolutional neural network (CNN). Inception V3, a deep learning model pre-trained on a massive image dataset (ImageNet), is renowned for its ability to automatically learn hierarchical visual features from images. It acts as a

powerful feature extractor, capturing intricate spatial details relevant to violence detection.

4.2 Temporal Stream (RNN - GRU):

a. Sequence Formation: The extracted spatial features from consecutive frames are organized into sequences. These sequences represent the temporal evolution of visual information within the video.

b. Feature Learning: The sequences are then passed to a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) network. GRUs are a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) specifically designed to capture long-term dependencies and temporal patterns in sequential data. In this context, the GRU learns to identify the temporal dynamics associated with violent actions.

4.3 Concatenation and Prediction:

a. Feature Fusion: The outputs of both the spatial and temporal streams are concatenated, combining spatial and temporal information into a unified representation.

4.4 Classification: This fused representation is fed into a fully connected layer followed by a softmax activation function. softmax layer outputs probabilities for each class (violent or non-violent), and the class with the highest probability is assigned as the final prediction for the video segment.

4.5 Data Validation: To train a machine learning model, data validation is required as a way provide a test for the model on unseen data. For that reason, hold-out validation technique which involves splitting the dataset into at least two parts (training and

validation data) was carried out. The model is trained on the training set and evaluated using the validation set. The model is tuned based on the performance of the model on the validation set. It is rather advised that the dataset is divided into three (3); training, validation and test sets. This is to counter the problem of information leak (Chollet, 2018). The dataset was divided into 70%, 20% and 10% for training, validation and test data were respectively. The dataset folder which initially consisted of two folders containing files of the two classes in consideration: Violent and Non-Violent. The folders are split using the python split-folder library. The new folder

structure now consists of three subfolders, train, val, and test. Each of them contains two subfolders holding violent and nonviolent videos. The splitting carried out resulted in the distribution of data as seen in the Table 2. As it is known beforehand that the dataset consists of two classes; Violent and Non-Violent videos, it is important to know the number of videos for each class. This statistic is important as it help decides the next cause of action to be taken. As can be seen from table 2, there is no significant difference between the number of images for both classes. This implies that there would be no need to handle the problem of data imbalance.

Table 2: Data split distribution for train, validation, and test.

No.	Data Split	Train	Validation	Test	Total
i.	Violence	252	72	37	361
ii.	Non-Violence	240	68	36	344
	Total	492	140	73	705

5.0 Results and Discussions

As the videos also are of different length, the number of frames from each would vary accordingly. Hence, a maximum sequence length i.e., frame size was set at 20 making those videos with above 20 frames compressed while those below 20 were padded with zero values. For the model learning in mini-batches, it would eventually learn to ignore the 0-padded entries, but it will waste learning cycles. Thus, there is a need for masking. Masking also helps to ensure that the loss function only considers real data (and not spurious data like that created by padding with zeros). The extracted frame features together with the applied mask would then jointly serve as During the training process, two values are frequently displayed: the network's loss over the training data and its accuracy over the same training data. It also shows that validation loss decreases over the loss. The validation accuracy increases over the accuracy during back propagation and validation. The model was able to learn from the available datasets.

Training batch size was alternated between 64, 32 and 16. The best performing batch size was observed to be 32. Training was set to run for 80 epochs as it was noted that there was any improvement on the

validation loss after that. Callbacks were also defined to be used for the models during training helping to give greater control of the training process. Two callbacks were applied for training all the models; Model Checkpoint and Reduce on Plateau. Model checkpoint is used to save the weight of a model at different points in time stating the file name to be used in saving and which of the weights to save. An obvious choice is to save the best checkpoint. Therefore, that was the choice in this work so as it can be loaded subsequently without having to retrain, the model. The model weights were saved as hdf5 file format. Reduce on plateau is applied to get out of a local minimum. This is done by reducing the learning rates. As defined in this project's code below, the learning rate of the model is to be reduced by one-third for every three epochs it fails to experience an increase in accuracy.

The training performance of the model was observed over the set epochs of 80. The training and validation accuracy showed a steady increase over the period while the train and validation loss decrease as required as shown in Fig 4. This shows that our model is well trained though it can perform better with increased training data.

```

] history, sequence_model = train_model()
Epoch 1: val_loss did not improve from 0.70438
1/2 [=====] - 91s/step - loss: 0.7016 - accuracy: 0.5102 - val_loss: 0.7070 - val_accuracy: 0.4857
Epoch 2: val_loss did not improve from 0.70438
1/2 [=====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.7104 - accuracy: 0.4848
Epoch 3: val_loss did not improve from 0.70438
1/2 [=====] - 9s/step - loss: 0.7142 - accuracy: 0.4694 - val_loss: 0.7092 - val_accuracy: 0.4857
Epoch 4/80
1/2 [=====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.7015 - accuracy: 0.5234
Epoch 4: val_loss improved from 0.70154 to 0.70033, saving model to /content/drive/MyDrive/Colab Notebooks/Violence detection Project/
1/2 [=====] - 10s/step - loss: 0.7003 - accuracy: 0.5001 - val_loss: 0.7015 - val_accuracy: 0.4857
Epoch 5/80
1/2 [=====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6977 - accuracy: 0.5111
Epoch 5: val_loss improved from 0.70033 to 0.69803, saving model to /content/drive/MyDrive/Colab Notebooks/Violence detection Project/
1/2 [=====] - 11s/step - loss: 0.6977 - accuracy: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6980 - val_accuracy: 0.4857
Epoch 6/80
1/2 [=====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6974 - accuracy: 0.5099
Epoch 6: val_loss improved from 0.69803 to 0.69587, saving model to /content/drive/MyDrive/Colab Notebooks/Violence detection Project/
1/2 [=====] - 11s/step - loss: 0.6958 - accuracy: 0.5000 - val_loss: 0.6964 - val_accuracy: 0.4857
Epoch 7/80
1/2 [=====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6968 - accuracy: 0.5195
Epoch 7: val_loss improved from 0.69587 to 0.69547, saving model to /content/drive/MyDrive/Colab Notebooks/Violence detection Project/
1/2 [=====] - 11s/step - loss: 0.6954 - accuracy: 0.5142 - val_loss: 0.6935 - val_accuracy: 0.5071
Epoch 8/80

```

Fig 4: Training process of the model

Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 shows the level of our model accuracy as it iterated 80 times and based on the results in both training and testing set, the accuracy increases in both sets and with almost the same level of advancement with the testing set even surpassing the training set, indicating the effectiveness of our model and no overfitting.

Fig. 5: Training and validation accuracy of the model.

Fig. 6: Training and validation loss of the model

When evaluating the performance of a model especially one related to classification of sensitive inputs like in this case violence, some important terms are frequently used. These terms include recall and precision. Before defining these, it is important to explain some other related terms. A true positive is an outcome where the model correctly predicts the positive class. Similarly, a true negative is an outcome where the model correctly predicts the negative class. A false positive is an outcome where the model incorrectly predicts the positive class. And a false negative is an outcome where the model incorrectly predicts the negative class (Google).

The recall of a test refers to the ability of the test to correctly identify those inputs with a given character tested that is violence in this case.

$$\text{Recall} = (\text{true positive}) / (\text{true positive} + \text{false negative})$$

Precision refers to the property of a test whereby it gives similar result on repeated analysis (Parikh, Annie, Shefali, Sekhar, & Ravi, 2008).

$$\text{Precision} = \text{true positive} / (\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive}).$$

Firstly, the model was used to make predictions on the 140 validation videos after training. This result was constructed in a confusion matrix which is a table that describes the performance of a classification model on a test data (Data School, 2014).

Fig. 7: Confusion Matrix obtained on the Validation Dataset.

In Fig 7, the model obtained 63 true negatives, 7 false negatives, 5 false positives and 65 true positives. Hence attaining an accuracy of 91.43% on the validation data. The corresponding precision is 92.86% while the recall is 90.28% as shown in the Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Accuracy, Precision and Recall Scores on the Validation Data.

The model built was again tested 73 unseen videos which had no chance of data leakage as it was not part of the training process. The corresponding confusion matrix obtained is shown in Fig. 9.

As can be seen from the Fig 9, the model obtained 35 true negatives, 3 false negatives, 3 false positives and 32 true positives. Hence attaining an accuracy of 91.78% on the test data. The corresponding precision and recall are both 91.43% as shown in the Fig. 10.

Fig. 9: Confusion matrix showing the distribution of predicted test videos.

Fig. 10: Accuracy, recall, and precision scores obtained on test data.

With the performance (accuracy, precision, and recall) roughly around the same range both on the

validation and test data sets, it confirms that the model had no issue of data leakage. A different

Jupyter notebook was created on Google Colab for testing on single videos. To test the saved model weights, it needed to be loaded on the model as defined previously. The video also needs to undergo similar data preparation process that was carried out on the training dataset. The model showed remarkable performance on two videos that were downloaded for individual testing. The first video is

a musical video (non-violent) while the second video is a karate fight (violent). As can be seen in the result obtained in Fig. 11, the model is not very certain at 86% in classifying the video as non-violent, this is because it contains some scenes that are close to violent. While the karate video was classified as violent with a high degree of certainty at 93%

```
[ ] test_video = '/content/drive/MyDrive/Colab Notebooks/Violence detection Project/Blindinglights.mp4'
print(f'Test video path: {test_video}')
test_frames = sequence_prediction(test_video)

Test video path: /content/drive/MyDrive/Colab Notebooks/Violence detection Project/Blindinglights.mp4
NonViolence: 86.09%
Violence: 14.86%

[ ] test_video2 = '/content/drive/MyDrive/Colab Notebooks/Violence detection Project/newf133.avi'
print(f'Test video path: {test_video2}')
test_frames = sequence_prediction(test_video2)

Test video path: /content/drive/MyDrive/Colab Notebooks/Violence detection Project/newf133.avi
Violence: 93.93%
NonViolence: 6.07%
```

Fig. 11: Result Showing Model Test on A Sample Video

6.0 Conclusion

Violent crime is currently a serious problem in many countries around the world including Nigeria. Many citizens have lost their lives due to late detection of criminal activities and late response by law enforcement agencies. Countries worldwide are adopting technology into areas like security, education, and management. The use of technology such as in detection and classification of violence would help in mitigating crime.

This paper presented a lightweight two-stream deep learning framework for violence detection in video streams, integrating Inception V3 for spatial feature extraction and a GRU for temporal modelling. The proposed architecture was evaluated on a unified dataset comprising the Movies Fight, Hockey Fight, and Violent Flows benchmarks, achieving 91.78% accuracy with 91.43% precision and recall on unseen test data, indicating strong generalization performance. The framework effectively distinguishes violent from non-violent scenes while maintaining computational efficiency suitable for real-time applications. However, the model exhibits reduced confidence in borderline scenarios, such as sports-related interactions, and its evaluation is limited to visual cues only. Future work will focus on expanding dataset diversity, incorporating multimodal

information, and validating deployment on edge-based surveillance systems.

Overall, the model's performance results indicated that the model made wrong predictions when it is difficult in deciding whether a scene is violent or non-violent for example in taekwondo. Therefore, additional moments just before or after such scenes would provide more context for the model, hence making improved predictions. The model from this research can benefit immensely to produce better results with increased datasets. It could also be deployed as a web and desktop application for easier use.

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